

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES ON INFECTION CONTROL AMONG STAFF NURSES AT A PRIVATE HOSPITAL: A BASIS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Preventing the spread of infectious diseases in hospital settings is the goal of infection control, a crucial component of healthcare. This study aimed to explore the knowledge and practices on infection control among staff nurses at a private hospital in Cauayan City, Isabela. It utilized a descriptive correlational design to systematically analyze the correlations between variables, specifically the knowledge and practices of infection control among staff nurses. The respondents were the 200 staff nurses selected through total enumeration. The researcher used an adapted questionnaire and utilized frequency and percentage distribution, mean, Spearman's Rho correlation, Mann-Whitney U test, and Kruskal-Wallis H test in treating the data. The demographic profile revealed that the nursing workforce is predominantly young and in the early stages of their careers, composed mostly of female nurses who hold a bachelor's degree and possess relatively limited clinical experience. In addition, staff nurses possess a strong foundational knowledge of infection control, particularly in hand hygiene, which is widely acknowledged as the most effective method to prevent healthcare-associated infections. Moreover, the staff nurses exhibit a commendable level of infection control practice, particularly in hand hygiene during high-risk procedures, indicating strong awareness of infection prevention protocols. The findings also revealed a significant yet weak positive correlation between nurses' infection control knowledge and their actual practices indicates that while increased knowledge tends to improve compliance, it is not the sole determinant of behavior. Lastly, there were no significant differences in infection control knowledge and practices among staff nurses across various demographic variables.

Keywords: *infection control, knowledge, practices, staff nurses*

INTRODUCTION

Preventing the spread of infectious diseases in hospital settings is the goal of infection control, a crucial component of healthcare. Patients and healthcare professionals are at serious risk from healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), which can result in longer hospital admissions, greater medical expenses, and higher death rates. As the front-line providers of patient care, nurses are essential to the implementation and observance of infection control procedures. Therefore, evaluating nursing staff members' infection control procedures and understanding is crucial to enhancing patient outcomes and preserving a secure atmosphere.

Infection control measures are integral to the hospital's operations. However, the effectiveness of these measures depends largely on the awareness and compliance of nursing staff, who are responsible for executing protocols such as hand hygiene, sterilization, and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE). Despite national guidelines and hospital policies aimed at reducing the risk of infections, there is a need to evaluate how well nurses understand and apply these practices in their daily work.

Globally, the rise of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) has prompted the need for stringent infection control measures across hospitals and medical centers. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) 2021, healthcare facilities worldwide face significant challenges with HAIs, contributing to prolonged hospital stays, increased medical costs, and higher mortality rates (Upadhyay & Smith, 2023). These trends have led to the development of international guidelines and protocols on infection control, emphasizing the importance of hand hygiene, sterilization, and isolation practices among healthcare providers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the knowledge and practices on infection control among staff nurses at a private hospital. More specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the staff nurses in terms of?
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Highest Educational Attainment;
 - 1.4 Years in Service; and
 - 1.5 Station/ Area of Assignment
2. What is the level of knowledge of staff nurses on infection control?
3. What are the practices of staff nurses on infection control?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the level of practice on infection control among staff nurses?

5. Is there a significant difference on the level of knowledge on infection control among staff nurses when grouped according to profile variables?

6. Is there a significant difference on the level of practice on infection control among staff nurses when grouped according to profile variables?

METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a descriptive correlational design. This design was selected to systematically analyze the correlations between variables, specifically the knowledge and practices of infection control among staff nurses. The descriptive correlational design effectively examined the relationships among many variables without manipulation. The study was conducted at a private hospital in Cauayan City, Isabela, a leading private healthcare facility in the region that provides a comprehensive range of medical services to the local community. The participants included a diverse sample of staff nurses representing various clinical departments and units within the hospital, such as the medical wards, surgical wards, pediatric unit, medical intensive care unit, emergency unit, operating room complex and hemodialysis unit. The population for this study consisted of the registered nurses (both permanent and probationary) employed at a selected private hospital in Cauayan City, Isabela. A total number of 200 nurses was included using a total enumeration sampling. An adopted survey questionnaire was used to collect data on the nurses' knowledge and practices related to infection control. The instrument consisted of two parts utilizing Likert scale questions to facilitate quantitative analysis.

Part 1 collected the demographic profile of the respondents, including their age, sex, highest educational attainment, years in service, and station/area of assignment. Part 2 focused on assessing the Knowledge and Practices of Infection Control among Staff Nurses. This section consisted of a 20-item questionnaire adapted from a previous study by Iliyasu et al. (2015). The scaling and scoring guide were slightly modified by the researcher. For Part 2.A. Knowledge of Infection Control among Staff Nurses, respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with a series of statements related to infection control knowledge, using a 4-point Likert scale where 4 represented "Strongly Agree," 3 represented "Agree," 2 represented "Disagree," and 1 represented "Strongly Disagree." Meanwhile, Part 2.B. Practices of Infection Control among Staff Nurses, respondents were asked to report the frequency of their infection control practices, using a 4-point Likert scale where 4 represented "Always," 3 represented "Often," 2 represented "Sometimes," and 1 represented "Never."

Since there was a modification, the researcher conducted validity and reliability tests. The researcher asked experts (chief nurse and nurse supervisors) to validate the tool. A score of 3.45 showed that the tool was highly valid. Additionally, pilot testing was conducted to test its internal consistency. A Cronbach's alpha score of 0.87 showed that the tool was reliable and accepted for administration to the respondents

RESULTS

Part 1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, highest educational attainment, years of experience, and number of trainings.

Table 1

Distribution of the Staff Nurses According to their Demographic Profile

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-30	166	83.0
31-40	33	16.5
41-50	1	0.5
Total	200	100
Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	34	17.0
Female	166	83.0
Total	200	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	194	97.0
Post-Graduate	6	3.0
Total	200	100
Years of Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1 year	81	40.5
1-3 years	85	42.5
4-6 years	10	5.0
7-9 years	13	6.5
10 years and above	11	5.5
Total	200	100
Area of Assignment	Frequency	Percentage
Medical-Surgical Wards	113	56.5
Pediatric Unit	17	8.5
Intensive Care Unit	22	11.0
Emergency Unit	17	8.5
Operating Room Complex	22	11.0
Hemodialysis Unit	9	4.5
Total	200	100
Status	Frequency	Percentage
Probationary	81	40.5
Regular	119	59.5
Total	200	100

As revealed in Table 1, the data on the age distribution of respondents reveals that a significant majority of the nursing staff (166 or 83%) fall within the 21-30 age group, indicating a generally young workforce. Only 33 or 16.5% are within the 31-40 age bracket, while very few between 41-50 years old, at 0.5%. This age profile suggests that the hospital primarily employs early-career nurses, which may reflect recent hiring trends or a youthful nursing population. In terms of sex, there is a notable imbalance, with females representing 166 or 83.0% and males comprising only 34 or 17.0% of the respondents. This mirrors the global trend of nursing being a female-dominated profession. While male representation remains low, their presence indicates a gradual shift toward more gender diversity in the field.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority (194 or 97.0%) of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree, with only 6 or 3.0% having completed postgraduate studies. This implies that most of the nurses meet the minimum required qualifications for practice, but relatively few have pursued further academic advancement. The years of experience data shows that a combined 83.0% of nurses have less than four years of experience (40.5% below one year and 42.5% with 1-3 years), highlighting a predominantly novice nursing workforce. The area of assignment data indicates that the majority are placed in the medical-surgical wards (113 or 56.5%), followed by equal distributions in the ICU and operating room complex (22 or 11.0% each), and smaller percentages in the pediatric, emergency, and hemodialysis units. Lastly, 81 or 40.5% of the nurses are on probationary status, while 119 or 59.5% are regular employees, which reflects a relatively balanced mix of new and established staff.

Part 2. Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control

Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the level of knowledge of staff nurses on infection control.

Table 2

Level of the Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control

	Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1	Hand hygiene is the most effective way to prevent healthcare-associated infections (HAIs).	3.96	Highly Knowledgeable
2	Using sterile gloves is crucial, but not the sole method for preventing HAIs.	3.63	Highly Knowledgeable
3	Wearing gloves does not replace the need for proper hand washing.	3.59	Highly Knowledgeable

4	Avoiding injuries from sharp objects is an essential part of infection control.	3.95	Highly Knowledgeable
5	I know that barrier precautions (such as wearing gloves, gowns, and masks) are critical for preventing infection transmission.	3.91	Highly Knowledgeable
6	I know that regular and correct hand hygiene practices are a key component of universal precautions.	3.96	Highly Knowledgeable
7	I know that the risk of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) transmission from a needle stick injury.	3.86	Highly Knowledgeable
8	I know the risk of Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) transmission from a needle stick injury.	3.92	Highly Knowledgeable
Statements		Mean	Verbal Description
9	I know the risk of Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) transmission from a needle stick injury.	3.77	Highly Knowledgeable
10	Post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) for blood borne pathogen exposure should begin within 72 hours of the incident.	3.72	Highly Knowledgeable
Category Mean		3.82	Highly Knowledgeable

Table 2 presents the level of knowledge among staff nurses regarding infection control. As shown, the two highest mean scores were observed in items 1, "Hand hygiene is the most effective way to prevent healthcare-associated infections," and 6, "I know that regular and correct hand hygiene practices are a key component of universal precautions," both with a mean of 3.96. Hand hygiene was emphasized as the best way to prevent healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) and its role in universal precautions. In addition, these results show nurses are well-versed in hand hygiene as a frontline defence.

In contrast, the two lowest mean scores were recorded in item no. 3 "Wearing gloves does not replace the need for proper hand washing" (M=3.59) and "Using sterile gloves is crucial, but not the sole method for preventing HAIs" (M=3.63). The first highlights the misconception that gloves can replace hand hygiene, and the second one discusses how sterile gloves help prevent infections. While the scores are still in the Highly Knowledgeable range, they reveal a relative gap in understanding the limitations of glove use and the importance of hand hygiene. There might be a need for education and clarification in this area through infection control updates or refresher courses.

Generally, the staff nurses demonstrated a high level of knowledge of infection control, with a category mean of 3.82, classified as Highly Knowledgeable. This shows respondents understand infection control principles, which is essential for ensuring patient safety and preventing the spread of infections. Their awareness reflects the positive outcomes of training programs, institutional policies, and clinical exposure to infection control practices. Even though nurses are usually well-informed, the slight variation in means suggests that professional development is still needed, especially in clarifying noteworthy practices, such as using gloves alongside hand washing. Infection control can be strengthened by ensuring it's not only known but also consistently and correctly practiced, ultimately leading to safer healthcare.

Table 3 illustrates the level of knowledge of staff nurses on infection control according to their profile variables.

Table 3

Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control According to their Profile

Profile Variables		Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control	
	Age	Mean	Verbal Description
	21-30	3.82	Highly Knowledgeable
	31-40	3.85	Highly Knowledgeable
	41-50	4.00	Highly Knowledgeable
	Sex	Mean	Interpretation
	Male	3.85	Highly Knowledgeable
	Female	3.82	Highly Knowledgeable
	Highest Educational Attainment	Mean	Interpretation
	Bachelor's Degree	3.82	Highly Knowledgeable
	Post-Graduate	3.82	Highly Knowledgeable
	Years of Experience	Mean	Interpretation
	Below 1 Year	3.81	Highly Knowledgeable
	1-3 Years	3.83	Highly Knowledgeable
	4-6 Years	3.98	Highly Knowledgeable
	7-9 Years	3.76	Highly Knowledgeable
	10 Years And Above	3.86	Highly Knowledgeable
	Area of Assignment	Mean	Interpretation
	Medical - Surgical Wards	3.81	Highly Knowledgeable
	Pediatric Unit	3.78	Highly Knowledgeable
	Intensive Care Unit	3.90	Highly Knowledgeable
	Emergency Unit	3.77	Highly Knowledgeable

Operating Room Complex	3.85	Highly Knowledgeable
Hemodialysis Unit	4.00	Highly Knowledgeable
Status	Mean	Interpretation
Probationary	3.81	Highly Knowledgeable
Regular	3.84	Highly Knowledgeable

According to Table 3, all nurses possess a high level of knowledge about infection control across all age groups. It's interesting to note that the highest mean was found in the 41-50 age group (M = 4.00), suggesting that more mature nurses may have developed deeper insights and practical wisdom through experience. Conversely, the 21-30 age group, which constituted most of the sample, had a slightly lower mean of 3.82 but was still classified as Highly Knowledgeable. This suggests that age likely affects infection control knowledge incrementally, possibly due to cumulative exposure and on-going learning.

Across sexes, female and male nurses had strong levels of knowledge, with mean scores of 3.85 and 3.82, respectively. This suggests that infection control awareness and training are effective regardless of sex, based on the minimal differences between sexes. As to educational attainment, both bachelor's and postgraduate degree holders achieved the same mean of 3.82, showing no significant variation in knowledge level based on education. According to this, the core infection control content at the undergraduate level is already sufficient for competent practice, so postgraduate studies might not add much to infection control knowledge unless they are directly related to infection prevention or advanced clinical practice.

Regarding years of experience, nurses with 4-6 years of experience had the highest mean (3.98), indicating that this group is at a point where theory is solidly backed up by practical experience. In contrast, those with 7-9 years had the lowest mean (3.76), which may be due to complacency or less frequent updating of infection control knowledge. This emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development in maintaining high standards of practice, regardless of the years served.

Additionally, there was considerable variation in the area of assignment. Hemodialysis and intensive care nurses scored the highest (4.00 and 3.90, respectively), likely due to the highly technical nature of these units and their strict infection control protocols. In contrast, those in the Emergency Unit and Pediatric Unit had the lowest mean knowledge scores (3.77 and 3.78), indicating that they could benefit from additional infection control training. Additionally, regular employees had a higher knowledge mean (3.84) than probationary nurses (3.81), suggesting that experience and time can make a difference in infection control. Although all groups were highly knowledgeable, slight variations suggest areas for refresher training and targeted interventions to enhance consistency in infection control practices.

Part 3. Level of Practice of Staff Nurses in Infection Control

Table 4 presents the level of infection control practices among staff nurses, highlighting their adherence to established protocols and standards.

Table 4

Level of Practice of Staff Nurses in Infection Control

	Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1	I wash my hands before and after using gloves.	3.74	Always Practiced
2	I wash my hands immediately after contact with any patient excretions or secretions.	3.91	Always Practiced
3	I wash my hands before and after performing any invasive procedures.	3.92	Always Practiced
4	I wash my hands between attending to different patients.	3.57	Always Practiced
5	I wear a cap and mask before performing any invasive procedures.	3.72	Always Practiced
6	I wear a long-sleeved gown during invasive procedures.	3.60	Always Practiced
7	I use sterile gloves before performing invasive procedures.	3.84	Always Practiced
8	I wear protective goggles before performing invasive procedures.	3.35	Always Practiced
9	I never recap needles after use to avoid needle stick injuries.	3.40	Always Practiced
10	I properly disinfect surfaces and equipment after each patient uses them.	3.80	Always Practiced
Category Mean		3.68	Always Practiced

Table 4 presents the level of practice among staff nurses regarding infection control. Out of ten indicators, "I wash my hands before and after performing any invasive procedures" (M=3.92) and "I wash my hands immediately after contact with any patient excretions or secretions" (M=3.91) had the highest mean scores. The results show that nurses are good at hand hygiene, especially in situations where contamination is high. The study suggests that nurses prioritize hand hygiene most when dealing with bodily fluids or invasive procedures, reflecting their awareness of the risks involved.

In contrast, the two lowest mean scores were "I wear protective goggles before performing invasive procedures" (M = 3.35) and "I don't recap needles after use" (M = 3.40). Despite still falling into the "Always Practiced" category, their lower means suggest

they're less consistent. The reason could be a lack of personal protective equipment, such as goggles, or the persistence of unsafe habits, like needle recapping, despite being aware of the risks. The findings suggest policy reminders, stricter supervision, and hands-on refresher training might be needed.

Based on the overall category mean of 3.68, staff nurses "Always Practiced" infection control measures, suggesting a commendable level of practice. Consistent practice reduces the risk of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), which reflects positively on the institution's infection control protocols and training. The high level of compliance also helps improve patient outcomes and staff safety, especially in high-risk units. The overall level of infection control among staff nurses is good; however, the slight variation in specific behaviours highlights the need for targeted interventions to improve performance. The practices related to eye protection and sharps disposal should be emphasized to ensure everyone's safety. Infection control practices will be uniformly high in the clinical environment if we strengthen these weaker areas through education and monitoring.

Table 5 presents the distribution of staff nurses' level of practice on infection control according to their profile variables.

Table 5

Level of Practice of Staff Nurses on Infection Control According to their Profile

Profile Variables	Level of Practices of Staff Nurses in Infection Control	
	Mean	Verbal Description
Age		
21-30	3.68	Always Practiced
31-40	3.67	Always Practiced
41-50	3.60	Always Practiced
Sex	Mean	Verbal Description
Male	3.66	Always Practiced
Female	3.69	Always Practiced
Highest Educational Attainment	Mean	Verbal Description
Bachelor's Degree	3.69	Always Practiced
Post-Graduate	3.52	Always Practiced
Years of Experience	Mean	Verbal Description
Below 1 Year	3.74	Always Practiced
1-3 Years	3.65	Always Practiced
4-6 Years	3.55	Always Practiced
7-9 Years	3.57	Always Practiced
10 Years And Above	3.71	Always Practiced
Area of Assignment	Mean	Verbal Description
Medical - Surgical Wards	3.70	Always Practiced
Pediatric Unit	3.63	Always Practiced
Intensive Care Unit	3.82	Always Practiced

Emergency Unit	3.60	Always Practiced
Operating Room Complex	3.69	Always Practiced
Hemodialysis Unit	3.38	Always Practiced
Status	Mean	Verbal Description
Probationary	3.74	Always Practiced
Regular	3.64	Always Practiced

As shown in Table 5, infection control practices are generally well maintained across ages, since all age groups fall under the verbal description "Always Practiced." In particular, the group of nurses under 21-30 had the highest mean of 3.68, which suggests excellent adherence among young nurses, possibly influenced by recent training or education. While still within the expected standard, the 41-50 age group posted the lowest mean of 3.60, which may suggest periodic refresher sessions to stay up to date on infection control protocol changes.

Nurses of both sexes demonstrated consistent compliance, with females slightly ahead (M=3.69) compared to males (M=3.66). The difference is minimal, so infection control practices are uniformly integrated regardless of sex. A positive reflection of institutional training and monitoring efforts to make sure infection control is not influenced by gender-based differences in clinical responsibilities.

With a bachelor's degree, nurses averaged 3.69, while those with a postgraduate degree averaged 3.52. It might be because fewer postgraduates are responding, or because both groups fall under "Always Practiced." This might be a result of a smaller number of postgraduates or their shift into administration or supervisory roles, which might result in fewer hands-on patient cares. It emphasizes that even highly educated nurses may benefit from periodic re-engagement with practical aspects of infection control.

According to years of experience, the below 1 year group had the highest mean at 3.74, showing that newer nurses are sticking to protocols more closely, likely due to recent training. Conversely, those with 4-6 years of experience had a lower mean of 3.55, possibly indicating complacency. The mean for nurses with 10 years or more was 3.71, which suggests that long-term experience can reinforce consistent practice.

Lastly, the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) staff had the highest mean at 3.82, emphasizing the importance of infection control in high-acuity areas. On the other hand, the Hemodialysis Unit had the lowest mean at 3.38, which may be a sign of gaps in training, resource limitations, or oversight. In comparing employment status, probationary nurses scored slightly higher (M=3.74) than regular employees (M=3.64), suggesting they're more cautious. The data confirms good compliance with infection control protocols across all profiles, but slight variations suggest continued monitoring, targeted reinforcement, and unit-specific interventions are needed to maintain and improve.

Part 4. Test on Significant Relationship between the Level of Knowledge and the Level of Practice on Infection Control Among Staff Nurses

Table 6 presents the test on significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the level of practice on infection control among staff nurses.

Table 6

Relationship between the Level of Knowledge and the Level of Practice on Infection Control among Staff Nurses

Variables		Practices
Knowledge	r	0.224
	p-value	0.001*

* $p < 0.05$

A Spearman's Rho correlation was used to determine the relationship between nurse knowledge and practice on infection control. A correlation coefficient of $r=0.224$ with a p-value of 0.001 indicates a weak but statistically significant positive relationship between the two variables. Thus, nurses' actual infection control practices tend to improve as their knowledge about infection control increases. With a p-value under 0.05, the result is considered significant, so the null hypothesis is rejected.

The weak correlation suggests that though knowledge contributes to better practice, it might not be the only determinant of behaviour in clinical settings. Infection control procedures may also be influenced by other factors, like institutional policies, infection control resources, supervision, workload, or even attitudes and habits. This means that having high knowledge doesn't always equate to perfect compliance or practice, highlighting the gap between what nurses know and what they do.

The findings suggest that training programs alone may not be enough to ensure high-level infection control practices among nurses. For better adherence to infection control protocols, interventions must address behavioural, environmental, and systemic factors as well. To reinforce the practical application of knowledge, hospital managers might consider mentoring, regular audits, feedback systems, and supportive supervision. By bridging the knowledge-practice gap, healthcare facilities can improve their infection control.

Part 5. Test on Significant Difference on the Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when Grouped According to Profile Variables

5.1 Age, Years of Experience, and Area of Assignment

Table 7 presents the test on significant difference on the level of knowledge of staff nurses on infection control when they are grouped according to their age, years of experience, and area of assignment.

Table 7

Differences on the Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when grouped according to Age, Years of Experience, and Area of Assignment

Age	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Level of Knowledge					
21-30	166	99.27	1.269	3	0.74
31-40	33	105.65			
41-50	1	148.50			
Years of Experiences	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Level of Knowledge					
Below 1 Year	81	97.08	6.591	4	0.16
1-3 Years	85	100.40			
4-6 Years	10	140.20			
7-9 Years	13	88.15			
10 Years And Above	11	104.95			
Area of Assignment	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Level of Knowledge					
Medical - Surgical Wards	113	94.60	3.066	5	0.12
Pediatric Unit	17	89.76			
Intensive Care Unit	22	119.68			
Emergency Unit	17	90.79			
Operating Room Complex	22	107.77			
Hemodialysis Unit	9	148.50			

A Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine whether Staff Nurses' Level of Knowledge on Infection Control significantly differed by their age, years of experience, and area of assignment. The results showed no statistically significant differences in knowledge levels across these demographic groups, since all p-values exceeded the significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that no matter how old they are, how much experience they have, or what kind of clinical area they work in, nurses' knowledge of infection control is consistent.

According to the result, infection control knowledge is likely disseminated uniformly across staff, which reflects effective institutional policies, standardized training programs, and equitable access to educational resources. This homogeneity ensures that all nurses,

no matter their background or work setting, are at the same level of infection prevention and patient safety. In addition, it could mean the organization's continuing education and in-service training are inclusive and standardized, helping to bridge any gaps that might arise due to age or experience differences.

Based on the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level, targeted interventions for improving knowledge may not need to be differentiated by age, experience, or assignment area. Instead, efforts can focus on maintaining the existing knowledge level across the board while addressing other factors that could influence infection control practices. Though knowledge seems uniform, it's important to make sure it's put into practice and reinforced through continuous training, supervision, and resources.

5.2 Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Status

Table 8 presents the test on significant difference on the level of knowledge of staff nurses on infection control when they are grouped according to their sex, highest educational attainment, and status.

Table 8

Differences on the Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when grouped according to Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Status

Category	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Level of Knowledge	Male	34	105.68	2646.000	0.54
	Female	166	99.44		

Category	Highest Educational Attainment	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Level of Knowledge	Bachelor's Degree	194	100.70	543.500	0.77
	Post-Graduate	6	94.08		

Category	Status	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Level of Knowledge	Probationary	81	97.08	4542.500	0.46
	Regular	119	102.83		

The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine if there were significant differences in the Knowledge Level of Staff Nurses regarding Infection Control based on their sex, highest educational attainment, and employment status. No statistically significant differences were found between the groups for any of the three variables, as the p-values all exceeded 0.05. As a result, nurses with different educational levels and

employment statuses, as well as both male and female nurses, demonstrate the same level of infection control knowledge.

No significant differences suggest that the hospital or institution has uniform training and education on infection control that reaches all staff members, regardless of gender, education, or employment status. The consistency of infection prevention standards throughout the healthcare facility depends on equity in knowledge dissemination. It also implies that personal demographics or formal education levels do not create disparities in understanding infection control measures, which is essential for ensuring a safe environment for both patients and healthcare workers.

The null hypothesis can be accepted at the 0.05 significance level, indicating that interventions to improve infection control knowledge do not need to target specific factors such as gender, education, or employment. Instead, educational efforts can continue to be applied universally to all nursing staff. Although knowledge is consistent across these groups, it's still crucial to reinforce it through continuous education and practical application so that expertise translates into effective infection control practices, thereby reducing the occurrence of healthcare-associated infections.

Part 6. Test on Significant Difference on the Level of Practice of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when Grouped According to Profile Variables

6.1 Age, Years of Experience, and Area of Assignment

Table 9 presents the test on significant difference on the level of practice of staff nurses on infection control when they are grouped according to their age, years of experience, and area of assignment.

Table 9

Differences on the Level of Practice of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when grouped according to Age, Years of Experience, and Area of Assignment

Age Level of Practice	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
21-30	165	100.63	1.728	3	0.63
31-40	33	98.85			
41-50	1	67.50			
Years of Experiences Level of Practice	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Below 1 Year	81	109.06	4.911	4	0.30
1-3 Years	85	97.58			
4-6 Years	10	78.80			
7-9 Years	13	82.19			
10 Years And Above	11	101.41			

Area of Assignment	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Level of Practice					
Medical - Surgical Wards	113	102.66	13.866	5	0.17
Pediatric Unit	17	83.29			
Area of Assignment	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Level of Practice					
Intensive Care Unit	22	124.70			
Emergency Unit	17	87.56			
Operating Room Complex	22	108.57			
Hemodialysis Unit	9	51.39			

The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to assess whether there were significant differences in staff nurse knowledge based on age, years of experience, and areas of assignment. As all p-values exceeded 0.05, there was no significant difference between the groups. As a result, nurses have a relatively uniform level of knowledge regarding infection control, regardless of their age, length of service, or clinical assignment.

This demonstrates the effectiveness of institutional efforts in ensuring standardized infection control education and training. In healthcare settings, consistency helps minimize knowledge gaps that could compromise patient safety and increase the risk of healthcare-associated infections. By maintaining an equitable knowledge base, the organization ensures that all nurses are equally capable of using infection control protocols, thereby promoting a safer and more reliable work environment.

Taking the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level suggests that interventions to improve infection control knowledge do not have to be customized for age, experience, or clinical area. Instead, nurses can get ongoing training to maintain and enhance their current knowledge levels. Although knowledge levels are consistent, healthcare leaders must monitor how knowledge is applied in practice and address other factors, such as attitudes, resources, and institutional support, which also impact infection control.

6.2 Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Status

Table 10 shows the test on significant difference on the challenges encountered by the staff nurses on endorsement practices when they are grouped according to their sex.

Table 10

Differences on the Level of Practice of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when grouped according to Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Status

Category	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
	Male	34	102.07	2768.500	0.86

Level of Practice	Female	166	100.18		
Category	Highest Educational Attainment	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Level of Practice	Bachelor's Degree	194	101.01	484.000	0.47
	Post-Graduate	6	84.17		
Category	Status	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Level of Practice	Probationary	81	109.06	4126.000	0.08
	Regular	119	94.67		

The Mann-Whitney U Test was conducted to examine whether there were significant differences in the level of practice of staff nurses on infection control when grouped according to sex, highest educational attainment, and employment status. This non-parametric test is appropriate for comparing two independent groups, especially when the data may not meet the assumptions required for parametric tests. The results revealed no statistically significant differences in infection control practices among the groups, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that male and female nurses, nurses with varying educational qualifications, and those with different employment statuses exhibit comparable infection control practices.

The lack of significant differences suggests that institutional policies and training programs on infection control are uniformly effective across all staff demographics. This uniformity is essential in healthcare settings, where consistent and proper practice of infection control measures directly impacts patient safety and the prevention of healthcare-associated infections. It also reflects that factors such as gender, education level, or employment status do not create disparities in how nurses apply infection control protocols, reinforcing the idea that these practices are well integrated into the nursing culture and standards within the organization.

Accepting the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level implies that targeted interventions to improve infection control practices may not need to be differentiated based on sex, educational attainment, or employment status. Instead, continuous reinforcement of infection control protocols through on-going training and supervision can be universally applied to all nursing staff. However, while practice levels appear consistent across these groups, healthcare leaders should continue to monitor and address other potential barriers—such as workload, resource availability, and behavioural factors—to ensure that knowledge and practices remain aligned for optimal infection control outcomes.

DISCUSSION

I. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of respondents reveals that most nurses are young and in the early stages of their careers. This age distribution suggests that a large percentage of hospital workers are recent hires or fresh graduates, a trend that may be driven by ongoing efforts to address workforce shortages. According to Bayuo et al. (2021), younger nurses bring energy, adaptability, and digital fluency to clinical practice, but they're also prone to burnout, stress, and limited clinical confidence. The implications for nursing management include enhanced mentorship programs, structured orientation, and supportive supervision to facilitate the transition of early-career nurses into professional roles.

The data also show that nursing is a gendered profession, with females making up a majority. This aligns with global patterns where nursing continues to be primarily perceived as a female profession (WHO, 2021). However, the presence of male nurses, although still a minority, indicates a slow but positive shift toward gender diversity. Studies like those by Zamanzadeh et al. (2022) suggest that gender diversity enriches team dynamics and enhances patient-centered care by promoting inclusivity and challenging stereotypes. Leaders in nursing must create an environment that supports both genders equally and provides everyone with an opportunity to grow.

According to education and experience data, most respondents hold bachelor's degrees, but very few have completed a master's degree. There's a gap in advanced academic preparation, which could impede professional development and clinical leadership. Additionally, the high percentage of nurses with less than four years of experience highlights the need for ongoing capacity building and other targeted strategies. According to Hu et al. (2022), novice nurses are more likely to experience job dissatisfaction and higher turnover intentions if they do not get enough support and opportunities. Additionally, nurses are spread across departments and employment statuses, reflecting the dynamic and transitional nature of the workforce, which requires leadership to balance staffing needs, workload equity, and employee development.

II. Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control

The findings indicate that staff nurses possess a strong foundational knowledge of infection control, particularly in hand hygiene, which is widely acknowledged as the most effective method to prevent healthcare-associated infections. This suggests the success of institutional education and training programs in instilling essential infection control principles. However, the lower scores on glove-related items highlight subtle yet critical misconceptions that may compromise practice if left unaddressed. The implication is that while baseline knowledge is high, targeted reinforcement on specific gaps—such as the proper use of gloves—is necessary. Institutions must ensure that training is dynamic, regularly updated, and reinforced through interactive learning and supervision. Doing so will not only maintain high standards but also close the knowledge-practice gap, ultimately

enhancing patient safety and supporting a culture of accountability and excellence in infection prevention.

III. Level of Practice of Staff Nurses on Infection Control

The findings demonstrate that staff nurses maintain a generally high level of infection control practice, particularly in hand hygiene, with the highest mean scores recorded for washing hands before and after invasive procedures and immediately after contact with bodily fluids. The results show that hand hygiene is prioritized during high-risk situations, underscoring a strong awareness of infection transmission routes. As Lai et al. (2020) point out, rigorous hand hygiene is a vital part of preventing healthcare-associated infections (HAI) in high-patient-interaction settings. A similar study by Adams et al. (2019) found that hand hygiene is one of the most effective measures to protect patients and healthcare workers.

However, the study also highlights relatively lower adherence to certain practices, such as wearing protective goggles before invasive procedures and avoiding the recapping of needles. This may be attributed to factors such as the unavailability of personal protective equipment (PPE), time pressures, or lingering unsafe habits. Both Alajmi et al. (2020) and Sabetian et al. (2021) found inconsistent PPE usage among healthcare workers is often related to logistics or complacency. In addition, recapping needles, a practice widely discouraged due to needle stick injuries, remains a challenge globally, often due to habit or a lack of safe disposal systems (Ashinyo et al., 2021). In order to eliminate unsafe practices, more focused policies, frequent monitoring, and refresher training are needed.

Overall, staff nurses demonstrate consistent infection control behavior. This is a positive indicator of the institution's commitment to patient and staff safety through effective protocols and education. According to Brooks et al. (2021), hospitals with a strong infection control culture report fewer HAIs and improved staff performance. Still, it is important to keep improving quality, even with high compliance. Mudenda et al. (2024) say strong infection prevention strategies shouldn't just reinforce existing best practices, but also plug any gaps where risk behaviors persist. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to practices like eye protection and sharps safety that are often overlooked.

To improve infection control standards, strategic interventions should be implemented. This could include hands-on simulations, peer-led workshops, or competency assessments focusing on PPE usage and safe handling of sharps. According to Powell-Jackson et al. (2020), real-time supervision and training make infection control more effective. Similarly, Kritsotakis et al. (2022) suggest healthcare institutions build a feedback system that reinforces desired behavior through regular audits. The importance of embedding infection prevention deeply into workplace culture so that all behaviors, including those related to less-practiced measures, align with safety rules. Through these measures, institutions can ensure uniformity in infection control practices, safeguarding both staff and patients.

IV. Relationship between the Level of Knowledge and Level of Practice on Infection Control among Staff Nurses

An analysis of Spearman's Rho correlation revealed a statistically significant but weak positive correlation between nurses' infection control practices and their knowledge of infection control practices. This finding indicates that as nurses' knowledge about infection control increases, their actual compliance with proper infection control practices also tends to improve, although not dramatically. Alhumaid et al. (2021) suggest that improving knowledge is a foundational step toward improving infection control behaviors, but knowledge alone doesn't guarantee behavior change.

The weak correlation coefficient implies that other variables may significantly influence infection control practices beyond knowledge. Factors such as institutional culture, availability of personal protective equipment, time constraints, managerial oversight, and nurses' attitudes or habits likely contribute to the consistency with which infection protocols are followed. Saha et al. (2020) and Saqlain et al. (2020) observed that even well-informed healthcare workers sometimes do not comply with infection control guidelines. The knowledge-practice gap highlights the difficulty of translating theoretical understanding into routine clinical behavior.

Given this, the findings suggest that infection control training should be part of a more comprehensive, multi-level strategy. Behavioral interventions, consistent leadership support, and systems that reinforce accountability must accompany educational efforts to achieve effective outcomes. According to Moodley et al. (2021), regular supervision, hands-on mentoring, and real-time feedback are essential to maintaining infection control behavior. Through ongoing evaluations, positive reinforcement, and removing logistical barriers, hospital administrators can foster an environment where knowledge is actively applied. Compliance and patient safety are more likely to improve with such integrated efforts.

V. Difference on the Level of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Infection Control when they are Grouped According to Profile Variables

The analysis revealed no significant difference in the level of knowledge on infection control among staff nurses when grouped by age, sex, educational attainment, years in service, or area of assignment. This suggests a relatively uniform distribution of knowledge, regardless of demographics. Such a finding may reflect the effectiveness of standardized training programs and institutional protocols that ensure all nurses, regardless of background or role, receive similar levels of infection control education. Having consistent infection prevention education across healthcare roles helps bridge knowledge gaps and promote equitable preparedness among healthcare workers, as noted by Alhumaid et al. (2021).

Additionally, when consistent workplace training is provided, variables traditionally assumed to influence knowledge, like experience and education level, may not be as important. Moodley et al. (2021) say regular in-service training and workplace-based

learning help nurses maintain their knowledge and skills. As a result, ongoing institutional reinforcement of infection control practices seems to equalize knowledge levels. In addition, hospitals that stress infection control protocols through mandatory training, simulations, and supervision likely create a culture where knowledge is retained.

However, while the findings point to homogeneity in infection control knowledge, this should not lead to complacency. According to Saha et al. (2020), infection control knowledge needs to be updated constantly to keep up with emerging pathogens and evolving guidelines. It is important for future training programs to keep being adaptive and responsive to new healthcare challenges, even if they produce uniform knowledge levels. To maintain current knowledge, healthcare institutions should invest in continuing education that fosters critical thinking and practical application in dynamic clinical scenarios. In this way, infection control practices remain effective and responsive, regardless of the nursing staff's demographics.

VI. Difference on the Challenges Encountered by the Staff Nurses during Endorsements when they are Grouped According to their Profile Variable

The absence of significant differences in the level of infection control practice among staff nurses, when grouped according to age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and area of assignment, suggests a uniformly strong adherence to infection control protocols across the workforce. This consistency may be attributed to institutional policies and regular training programs that standardize infection control expectations for all nurses, regardless of demographic background. As noted by Alajmi et al. (2020), uniform infection control guidelines and continuous reinforcement within healthcare settings help promote consistent behaviors, thereby reducing variability in practice across different staff profiles.

Additionally, the lack of significant difference based on years in service or area of assignment highlights the success of orientation programs and competency assessments that are typically required for both new and experienced staff across all departments. According to Mudenda et al. (2024), structured infection control training integrated into onboarding and ongoing education efforts ensures that even less experienced nurses or those working in high-risk units adhere to the same standards. This finding reflects the effectiveness of workplace-based interventions and supervision in maintaining a uniform practice, regardless of a nurse's tenure or clinical assignment.

However, while uniformity is beneficial, it should not negate the need for continuous quality improvement and department-specific infection control audits. Lai et al. (2020) argue that even in environments where practice appears consistent, contextual challenges such as workload, patient acuity, and resource availability can have a subtle impact on adherence. Therefore, infection control programs must remain dynamic, with targeted support where lapses are most likely to occur. The uniformity in practice observed in this study is encouraging. Still, sustained vigilance through monitoring, feedback, and department-specific interventions remains essential to ensure ongoing compliance and responsiveness to emerging threats.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

The demographic profile revealed that the nursing workforce is predominantly young and in the early stages of their careers, composed mostly of female nurses who hold a bachelor's degree and possess relatively limited clinical experience. This suggests a dynamic yet developing group of professionals who bring fresh perspectives and enthusiasm to patient care, but who may also require continued guidance, mentorship, and professional development to fully mature in their roles.

Staff nurses demonstrate strong knowledge of infection control, especially hand hygiene, reflecting the effectiveness of institutional training programs. However, lower scores on glove-related items indicate gaps that could compromise practice. This implies the need for ongoing reinforcement and targeted training on specific areas, such as proper glove use, to bridge the knowledge-practice gap, enhance patient safety, and sustain a culture of excellence in infection prevention.

Staff nurses demonstrate strong infection control practices, particularly in hand hygiene, reflecting effective training and adherence to protocols. However, lower compliance in areas like wearing protective goggles and avoiding needle recapping highlights gaps that need attention. This implies the need for continuous reinforcement, targeted retraining, and adequate PPE to sustain and improve infection control, ensuring the safety of both healthcare workers and patients.

The weak yet significant positive correlation between nurses' infection control knowledge and practices indicates that knowledge alone does not ensure compliance. This implies that hospitals must complement education with behavioral support, adequate resources, and active supervision to reinforce proper practices, reduce infection risks, and ensure safer patient care.

The uniform infection control knowledge across demographic and professional factors reflects the effectiveness of institutional training. This implies that healthcare institutions should continue dynamic, evidence-based education to maintain current, practical, and actionable knowledge for all staff nurses. Also, the uniform infection control practices across staff nurses highlight effective institutional training and a shared culture of safety. This implies that healthcare institutions must sustain compliance through ongoing audits, feedback, and adaptive strategies to maintain high standards and safeguard both patients and staff.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proposed to enhance practice, guide policy development, and inform future interventions:

1. Conduct refresher training and visual reminders to reinforce that wearing gloves is not a substitute for proper hand washing before and after patient care.
2. Implement regular monitoring, audits, and reminders to ensure staffs consistently wash hands even when using gloves, promoting strict adherence to infection control protocols.
3. Conduct regular training sessions and practical demonstrations emphasizing the importance of wearing protective goggles during all invasive procedures to prevent eye exposure to infectious materials.
4. Provide refresher workshops and visual reminders on proper needle handling, specifically highlighting the prohibition of needle recapping to prevent needle stick injuries.
5. Implement reminders, supervision, and monitoring strategies to ensure hand washing is consistently performed between attending to different patients, reinforcing its critical role in infection prevention.
6. Establish routine audits and real-time feedback mechanisms to identify lapses in infection control practices, addressing gaps promptly to maintain high standards of safety and patient care.
7. Future researchers are encouraged to explore the assessment or evaluation of head nurses, nurse supervisors, or the chief nurse regarding the infection control knowledge and practices of staff nurses. This expanded perspective could provide a more comprehensive understanding of staff nurses' knowledge and practice.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical approval for the study was secured from the institutional review board of the selected private hospital in Cauayan City, Isabela to ensure the study adhered to ethical standards and principles. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, guaranteeing their full comprehension of the study's aims and objectives, as well as their right to withdraw from the study at any moment without facing any repercussions. The confidentiality of participants' responses was preserved throughout the entire research process, protecting the privacy and anonymity of the nursing staff who took part in the study.

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